

PAPER 9

**Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education
Institutions through Stage Models**

P. S. Aithal & P.M. Suresh Kumar

**IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business
Management,**

Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 121 - 130, March 2015
ISSN 2347-4572, **I.F. 1.54**

ENHANCEMENT OF GRADUATE ATTRIBUTES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS THROUGH STAGE MODELS

P. S. AITHAL¹ & P. M. SURESH KUMAR²

¹Department of Business Management, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore, India

²Department of Social Work, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore, India

ABSTRACT

The higher education institutions should clearly define and set mechanisms to monitor the learning outcomes. The student SWOT Analysis is one of the important basis to find out their skills, strengths, interest in activities, career objectives and expectations from the institute. This will be used as a reference to monitor the student progress and achievement of learning outcome. Additionally, the institution can develop a model of student development and enhance graduate attributes by means of focused development plan. In semester based courses, the institution can identify various attributes essential for earning such degree and focus on a particular attribute in each semester. Based on our experience at SIMS, we have developed a stage model for all the courses to focus on a particular graduate attribute during each semester by designing the programmes in such a way that at the end of the course students possess the expected graduate attributes. In this paper, the stage models developed for three post graduate courses namely Business Management (MBA⁺⁺), Computer Applications say (MCA⁺⁺), Social work (MSW⁺⁺), and three undergraduate courses in Business Management say BBM⁺⁺, Computer Applications say (BCA⁺⁺), & in Commerce (B.Com⁺⁺) are presented and the contributions of these models for enhancement of graduate attributes are discussed.

KEYWORDS: Graduate Attributes, Higher Education, Stage Model

INTRODUCTION

The higher education institutions should clearly define and set mechanisms to monitor the learning outcomes. The student SWOT Analysis is one of the important basis to find out their skills, strengths, interest in activities, career objectives and expectations from the institute. This will be used as a reference to monitor the student progress and achievement of learning outcome. Additionally, the institution can develop a model of student development and enhance graduate attributes by means of focused development plan. In semester based courses, the institution can identify various attributes essential for earning such degree and focus on a particular attribute in each semester. Based on our experience at SIMS, we have developed a stage model for all the courses to focus on a particular graduate attribute during each semester by designing the programmes in such a way that at the end of the course students possess the expected graduate attributes. Master of Business Administration (MBA) is a programme intended to groom professionals to manage business. Among the tasks in any business is planning, organizing, directing, staffing and controlling. Since any business has got to put together men, machine, material and money, for the attainment of results those managing the activity should acquire competency in knowledge and skill in decision making. In order to groom area-focused specialists the course offers to meet finer requirements through specializations in production, finance, marketing and human resource. A proliferation of institutions offering the course is a direct implication of the growing demand for trained personnel in the field of managing

business. Justifiably enough most institutions have introduced value additions to reinforce the relevance and strength of the course. Of late, the cry for quality has brought forward the ++ model in various under graduate and post graduate courses, which is competency building through ‘stage based quality assurance strategy’ that promotes bridging curriculum gaps, imparting skills and creating a mindset favourable to managing business or work as entrepreneurs. In this paper, the stage models developed for three post graduate courses namely Business Management (MBA⁺⁺), Computer Applications say (MCA⁺⁺), Social work (MSW⁺⁺), and three undergraduate courses in Business Management say BBM⁺⁺, Computer Applications say (BCA⁺⁺), & in Commerce (B.Com⁺⁺) are presented and the contributions of these models for enhancement of graduate attributes are discussed.

STAGE BASED MODELS

(1) MBA⁺⁺ Model

Figure 1 : MBA⁺⁺ Model

This is a four stage model as given in figure 1, run through the entire course to bring about growth through a time bound and stage based strategy. The first of this is to build confidence through communication power augmented through field exposure, interaction with industry experts and case study analysis. In the second stage the students are encouraged to identify fields suited to their talents to orient towards direction, a process facilitated by the faculty to help the students realize and arrive at one’s own potential. Just as a war cannot be won without a strategy however massive its strength be, a business person cannot succeed without being a strategist. The third stage is by converting students into a strategic innovator through team exercises and group competitions in planning strategies. This is largely through innovations since strategy in one context is not the right fit for another context or time. Most of the ills of any business or day to day life is lack of appropriate decision or decision at the appropriate time. The final stage in the model is to foster decision making. Business cannot wait for time. The flair in decision making converts the professional for successful take off. The details of value added programmes during each semester/course of MBA programme are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Details of Value Added Part in MBA Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	3 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	2 in each semester
3	Workshops	3 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05

Table 1: Contd.,

6	Soft skill Programme	1/week
7	Guest Lectures	06 in each semester
8	Industry visits	1/team
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	1/subject
10	Study Material book	1/subject
11	Enrichment Programmes	3/semester
12	Student Project	1/semester
13	Business Newspaper analysis	2 teams/week
14	Student Presentation	4 teams/week
15	Placement related programme	1/week
16	Student Forum activities	01/week
17	Student Specialization exhibition	04/semester
18	Faculty Development Programme	04/semester
19	Student exchange programme	01/year
20	Team based activities/programmes	04/semester

(2) MSW⁺⁺ ModelFigure 2: MSW⁺⁺ Model

In **MSW⁺⁺ model** as shown in figure 2, the curriculum and the pedagogy are designed in such a way to create a mindset for social service profession. Through properly planned orientation programme, field visits, field work practicum, university subjects, value added chapters, certificate programmes, modular programmes, workshops, guest lectures and co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, students are prepared to focus their mindset and love the social work service as a profession. The students study five compulsory subjects and carryout field work practicum in a reputed NGO depending on their choice as a part of university syllabus. The details of the curriculum are given in Table 2 to 5. The details of value added programmes during each semester of MSW programme are listed in Table 6.

Table 2: First Semester Subjects of MSW Course as per University Curriculum

S.No.	Subject	Teaching Hours	Maximum Marks Allotted
1	Social work - History & Philosophy	4 hours/week	100
2	Working with individuals & families	4 hours/week	100
3	Working with groups	4 hours/week	100
4	Dynamics of human behaviour	4 hours/week	100
5	Social work practicum	16 hours/week	225

Table 3: Second Semester Subjects of MSW Course as per University Curriculum

S.No.	Subject	Teaching Hours	Maximum Marks Allotted
1	Indian Society	4 hours/week	100
2	Working with communities	4 hours/week	100
3	Social work research & Statistics	4 hours/week	100
4	Social & Organizational Psychology	4 hours/week	100
5	Social work practicum	16 hours/week	225

Table 4: Third Semester Subjects of MSW Course as per University Curriculum

S.No.	Subject	Teaching Hours	Maximum Marks Allotted
1	Management of Organizations	3 hours/week	100
2	Communications skills in social work practice	3 hours/week	100
3	Specialization I	3 hours/week	100
4	Specialization II	3 hours/week	100
5	Social work practicum	3 hours/week	225

Table 5: Fourth Semester Subjects of MSW Course as per University Curriculum

S.No.	Subject	Teaching Hours	Maximum Marks Allotted
1	Project planning & Management	3h/week	100
2	Specialization I	3h/week	100
3	Specialization II	3h/week	100
4	Research Project	3h/week	100
5	Social work practicum	3 days/week	225

Table 6: Details of Value Added Part in MSW Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	3 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	2 in each semester
3	Workshops	3 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05
6	Soft skill Programme	1/week
7	Guest Lectures	06 in each semester
8	Out bound social program for publics	1/team
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	05
10	Study Materials	05

(3) MCA⁺⁺ Model

In **MCA⁺⁺ model** as shown in Figure 3, in the first semester, the curriculum and the pedagogy are designed in such a way to build their logic to develop better software. Through properly planned orientation programme, IT industry visit, university subjects, value added chapters, certificate programmes, modular programmes, workshops, guest lectures, group & team projects, and co-curricular & extra-curricular activities, students are prepared to think logically to apply their mind to software problems. The students study five compulsory subjects and 2 laboratory practical papers as a part of their university syllabus. Similarly in the second semester, the curriculum, the pedagogy and the value added programs are designed in such a way to develop the students as system programmers. In third semester, the effort is made to train students in open source platform to learn and develop open source programme based applications. In the fourth semester,

MCA students will learn various database management software leading to database developers. Web programming, web design and management are very important areas in software profession and the curriculum and the pedagogy are designed in such a way the MCA students in fifth semester will become efficient web developers. Finally, in the sixth semester, students are sent to various software companies to understand the design and development of new application software individually for six months so that they are trained to become perfect software engineer. The details of value added programmes during each semester of MCA programme are listed in Table 7.

Figure 3: MCA⁺⁺ Model

Table 7: Details of Value Added Part in MCA Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	3 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	2 in each semester
3	Workshops	3 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05
6	Soft skill Programme	1/week
7	Guest Lectures	06 in each semester
8	Out bound social program for publics	1/semester
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	01/subject
10	Study Materials	01/subject
11	Institutional team software projects	01/semester
12	Software Industry visits	01/semester
13	Student based competitions	01/semester
14	Student Presentations	01/student/semester

(4) B.Com⁺⁺ Model**Figure 4: B.Com. ⁺⁺ Model**

The value added B.Com. model called B.Com. ⁺⁺ is shown in Figure 4. In first semester, B.Com. students study six subjects as per university curriculum and institutional value added programmes with focus on developing analytical skills for critical thinking. In second semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to instill traits for modern bankers. In third semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to develop human resources for industry and commerce. In fourth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed to create an opportunity for international trade & commerce. In fifth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to prepare students as financial decision makers and tax consultants. In sixth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to prepare them effective accountants and auditors. The details of value added programmes during each semester of B.Com. programme are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Details of Value Added Part in B.Com. Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	1 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	1 in each semester
3	Workshops	1 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05
6	Soft skill Programme	1/month
7	Guest Lectures	02 in each semester
8	Industry visits	1/team
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	05
10	Study Materials	05
11	Institutional team Project work	01/semester
12	Organizing competitions	01/semester
13	Subject based exhibition	01/semester

5. BBM⁺⁺ Model

Figure 5: BBM⁺⁺ Model

The value added BBM model called BBM.⁺⁺ is shown in Figure 5. In first semester, BBM students study six subjects as per university curriculum and institutional value added programmes with focus on inception of management thought. In second semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to inculcate business ethics. In third semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to erudition of corporate laws. In fourth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with knowledge to manage people, money and systems. In fifth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to prepare students as risk analyst. In sixth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to prepare them as efficient entrepreneurs and business executives. The details of value added programmes during each semester of BBM programme are listed in Table 9.

Table 9 : Details of Value Added Part in BBM Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	1 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	1 in each semester
3	Workshops	1 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05
6	Soft skill Programme	1/month
7	Guest Lectures	02 in each semester
8	Industry visits	1/team
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	01/subject
10	Study Materials	01/subject
11	Institutional team Project work	01/semester
12	Organizing competitions	01/semester
13	Subject based exhibition	01/semester

6. BCA⁺⁺ Model

The value added BCA model called BCA⁺⁺ is shown in Figure 6. In first semester, BCA students study five theory subjects, two laboratory based subjects as per university curriculum and institutional value added programmes with focus on building foundation on computer science/IT fundamentals. In second semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to building interest in diverse IT fields & communication. In third semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to develop different IT skill sets. In fourth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed in guiding students with networking, e-commerce & graphics. In fifth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to boosting students to face competitive challenges. In sixth semester along with university curriculum, the value added programmes are designed with an emphasis to prepare them as skilled perfect software programmers. The details of value added programmes during each semester of BCA programme are listed in Table 9.

Figure 6: BCA⁺⁺ Model

Table 9: Details of Value Added Part in BCA Programme

S. No.	Type of Programme	Number
1	Certificate Programme	1 in each semester
2	Modular Programme	1 in each semester
3	Workshops	1 in each semester
4	Vivekananda Study Circle programmes	02
5	Value added Chapters	05
6	Soft skill Programme	1/month
7	Guest Lectures	02 in each semester
8	Industry visits	1/team
9	Teaching Plan Booklet	05
10	Study Materials	05
11	Institutional team Project work	01/semester
12	Organizing competitions	01/semester
13	Subject based exhibition	01/semester

ADVANTAGES OF STAGE BASED MODELS

The above models helps the Institute to ensure the achievement of learning outcomes such as emotional maturity, social maturity, business acumen, professionalism and intellectual capabilities. The value added programmes are designed in each semester to accomplish the stated objectives of that stage. Based on University syllabus and value added programmes designed in each semester, the students progress is evaluated and monitored to promote the students to the next stage. It is observed that students who undergo training as per stated Stage Model would be able to show better performance both in curricular and competitive exams to get better job/higher educational opportunities through enhanced graduate attributes.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the stage models developed for three post graduate courses in Business Management (MBA⁺⁺), in Computer Applications say (MCA⁺⁺), in Social work (MSW⁺⁺), and three undergraduate courses in Business Management say BBM⁺⁺, Computer Applications say (BCA⁺⁺), & in Commerce (B.Com⁺⁺) are presented and the contributions of these models for enhancement of graduate attributes through better performance both in curricular and competitive exams to get better job/higher educational opportunities are discussed.

REFERENCES

- I. M. Joseph, M. Yakhou, G. Stone, An educational institution's quest for service quality: customers' perspective. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 13 No. 1, 2005, 66-82.
- II. F. Hill, (1995). Managing service quality in higher education: the role of the student as primary consumer. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 3 No. 3, 1995, 10-21.
- III. L. Harvey and D. Green, "Defining Quality," *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol. 18, No. 1, 1993, 9-34.
- IV. G. Srikanthan, J. Dalrymple, (2002). Developing a holistic model for quality in higher education. *Quality in Higher Education*, Vol. 8 No. 3, 2002, 215-245.
- V. C. Douglas Bennett, "Assessing Quality in Higher Education," *Liberal Education*, Spring 2001, 40-46.
- VI. D. George Kuh, Jillian Kinzie, John H. Schuh, Elizabeth J. Whitt Student Success in College: Creating Conditions That Matter, *Wiley Publishers*, 2005, ISBN 978 -0-470-59909-9.
- VII. Karen E. Hinton, A Practical Guide to Strategic Planning in Higher Education, Society for College and University Planning, www.scup.org, 2012, ISBN 978-1-937724-13-9.
- VIII. Paul D. Umbach, Matthew R. Wawrzynski, Faculty do Matter: The Role of College Faculty in Student Learning and Engagement, *Research in Higher Education*, Volume 46, Issue 2, March 2005, 153-184.
- IX. Boyce, Mary E., "Organizational Learning is Essential to Achieving and Sustaining Change in Higher Education", *Innovative Higher Education*, Vol. 28, No. 2, 2003, 119-136.
- X. James Hiebert, Anne K. Morris, Teaching, Rather Than Teachers, As a Path Toward Improving Classroom Instruction, *Journal of Teacher Education* vol. 63 no. 2, March/April 2012, 92-102.